

Scientific Research – Opportunities and Pitfalls

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He [God] has made everything beautiful in its time. Also, he has put eternity into man's heart, yet so that he cannot find out what God has done from the beginning to the end.

(Solomon, Bible, Eccl. 3:11, ESV)

Introductory note: On Saturday, 21st of October 2023, in the Europa House in Tokyo, the first Symposium of European Researchers in Japan took place under the title: “Past, Present and Future Cross-continental Connections between Europe and Japan”. In the first technical session in the morning with the topic: “Dependence of Societies on Scientific Research”, I gave a lecture on “Scientific Research - Opportunities and Pitfalls”, about which I report here.

Opportunity 1: Passive House

The first opportunity of scientific research I want to mention is the *development of the Passive House concept* since 1990. It is founded on the following five physics-based concepts (see Fig. 1): insulation, avoidance of thermal bridges, insulating heat gain windows (Passive House windows), heat recovery ventilation, and air tightness [1]. This development is spearheaded by The Passive House Institute (PHI), an independent research institute founded 1996 by Prof. Dr Wolfgang Feist, with a continuously growing interdisciplinary team of employees. PHI has played an especially crucial role in the development of the Passive House concept. The first pilot project (1990) was Europe's first inhabited multi-family house to achieve a documented heating energy consumption of below 10 kWh/(m²a), i.e. per square meter and year, a consumption level confirmed through over 30 years of detailed monitoring. Regarding its international adoption around the world, the Passive House concept itself remains the same for all of the world's climates, as does the physics behind it. Of course, the details do have to be adapted to the specific climate at hand and will look much different in Alaska compared to Zimbabwe. A current example is, e.g., the new Gewerbepark Gablingen (north of Augsburg in Bavaria): constructed in 2023, with an annual heating demand of 17 kWh /m², and a total floor area of 3723 m². [2,3]

Fig. 1. The five passive house construction concepts based on physics. [4]

Opportunity 2: Attosecond light pulses for the study of electron dynamics in matter

The second opportunity was recognized with the Nobel Prize in Physics of 2023, which was awarded to Pierre Agostini, Ferenc Krausz and Anne L’Huillier "for experimental methods that generate *attosecond pulses of light for the study of electron dynamics in matter*." This year’s Nobel Prize in Physics opens windows that were unimaginable to Heisenberg, to explore phenomena that were previously impossible to observe. In the world of electrons, changes occur in a few tenths of an attosecond – an attosecond is so short that there are as many in one second as there have been seconds since the birth of the universe. Attosecond pulses can also be used to identify different molecules, such as in medical diagnostics. By combining broadband optics, ultrafast laser sources, and precision femtosecond-attosecond field resolving technologies, the Krausz group (Max Planck Institute of Quantum Optics, Garching) has developed electric-field molecular fingerprinting that can detect changes in molecular composition of biofluids. This holds promise as a new *in vitro* diagnostic analytical technique to detect characteristic molecular traces of diseases in blood samples. The great advantage is that many molecules can be monitored at the same time, and the radiation is non-ionizing and therefore not harmful. [5]

Opportunity 3: Virtual reality surgery training

The third opportunity is *virtual reality surgery training*. The deep-tech venture company ORamaVR was created to tackle a major health crisis that is currently affecting almost five billion people globally: the lack of access to affordable surgical care. This health crisis is the direct result of a lack of innovation in

medical training over the last 150 years that has meant that the profession cannot keep up with the demand. The WHO is projecting that by 2030, there will be a staggering deficit of 18 million medical professionals. Meanwhile, the number of fatal medical errors keeps rising due to the fact that medical training is highly intensive: a master/educator operates on a patient and the trainee/apprentice observes and learns on-the-job, often practicing on real patients. Medical extended reality (XR) training can change all that. ORamaVR has attracted substantial deep-tech R&D grants from the European Commission and boasts important research and industrial partnerships, including Airbus, Telefonica, CNRS and Eurescom. [6]

In the second half I describe some of the severe pitfalls of modern science.

Pitfall 1: Hypersonic cruise missiles and glide vehicles

A graph from a standard college level physics textbook (H. Oertel, *Prandtl-Essentials of Fluid Mechanics*, Springer, Heidelberg, 2010, Fig. 4.177.) shows the ratio of lift to drag coefficient c_l/c_w of aerodynamic vehicles over Mach numbers (speed measured in units of the speed of sound of 343m/s, i.e. $M=1$ means $v = 343\text{m/s}$) from $M = 0$ to 5, showing with increasing Mach number: the swept wing of jet planes, the delta wings of fighter planes (and the now decommissioned Concorde) and the modern wave glider (still under development). Intercontinental ballistic missile (ICBM) trajectories reach up to 1200 km and follow easily predictable ballistic trajectories, which enables their interception. Different from that, hypersonic cruise missiles fly only 20-30 km high (dodging radar), travel with over $M > 5$ and are maneuverable, making them difficult to intercept. In 2018 Russia successfully tested a hypersonic glide vehicle that can be equipped with a nuclear war head and reached the speed of $M = 27$, meaning it can cover the distance from Moscow to Washington in merely 14 min, is maneuverable and flies at altitudes of 40-100 km. Japan aims at the development of a hypersonic glider by 2026. [7]

Pitfall 2: Genome editing

The second pitfall may be *genome editing* for which Emmanuelle Charpentier and Jennifer A. Doudna jointly received the 2020 Nobel prize in chemistry. They were able to change the CRISPR part of the genetic scissors so that its code matches the code where the cuts are to be made with overwhelming results. The DNA molecules were cleaved in exactly the right places. Several research groups around the world demonstrated that this tool can be used to modify the genome in cells from both mice and humans, which lead to an explosive development. Because this gene tool is so easy to use, it is now widespread in basic research. It is used to change the DNA of cells and laboratory animals. In medicine, the genetic scissors are contributing to new immunotherapies for cancer. [8]

Alongside all their benefits, genetic scissors can also be misused. For example, this tool can be used to create genetically modified embryos. One thing is certain: these genetic scissors affect us all. We will face new ethical issues. [8]

There may indeed be a sinister relationship to the Covid pandemic of the last three years. The Times (UK) newspaper reported on 2023/06/11: “Dr Steven Quay, a US scientist who advised the State Department on its investigation ... believes Covid-19 was created by inserting a furin cleavage site into one of the mine viruses [taken from bats in a mine in China] and then serial passaging it through humanised mice.” [9] In this case opportunity and pitfall seem to be inseparable like two sides of a coin.

Pitfall 3: Surveillance technology

The third pitfall example that affects us all is *21st century surveillance technology* as revealed by Washington Post journalist and Winner of the Pulitzer Prize Barton Gellman in his bestseller “Dark Mirror – Edward Snowden and the American Surveillance State” [10]. Edward Snowden touched off a global debate in 2013 when he gave Barton Gellman, Laura Poitras, and Glenn Greenwald each a vast and explosive archive of highly classified files revealing the extent of the American government’s access to our every communication. The book provides a gripping inside narrative of investigative reporting as

it happened and a deep dive into the machinery of the surveillance state. [11] It is partly a thriller about reporting the secrets the US government hoped to keep, partly a deeper exposé about the vast power the surveillance state built to pierce Americans' privacy with a few keystrokes. This book is a deep exploration of a surveillance apparatus of unimaginable magnitude, the scope of the NSA global snooping campaign he revealed is more shocking than ever. [12]

PRISM (Planning Tool for Resource Integration, Synchronization and Management): Microsoft, Yahoo, Google, Facebook, PalTalk ..., YouTube, Skype, AOL and Apple all agreed to cooperate, according to the leaked documents between 2007 and 2012. And what are they supposedly taking from those servers? Well, e-mail, chats (video or voice), videos, photos, stored data, Skype conversations, file transfers, logins, social networking. Everything. [13] A diagram showing an overview of the PRISM surveillance system and its work flow can be found in [14].

Conclusion

I conclude with a remark on the ambivalence of science. Opportunities reviewed here are to sustain life, diagnose and cure disease. Examples of serious pitfalls are the destruction of life, creation of disease and total surveillance. A thoughtful observer wrote: "... there is the Promethean desire to use science and technology not so much to tame 'nature' but to dominate it to the point of destruction or, as [C.S.] Lewis puts it in 'The Abolition of Man' [16], 'The power of Man to make himself what he pleases means, as we have seen, the power of some men to make other men what they please.'" [15]

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Footnotes and References

[1] For a good overview of the 5 concepts of a passive house see: W. Feist, *Energy Efficiency – The Global Contribution of the Passive House Standard*, in E. Hitzer, G.C. Kimura, M. Shukuya, A. Takeuchi (eds.), Foreword by P. Hastings, *持続可能な 世界のために For a Sustainable World*, Bookmundo Osiander, Tuebingen, 2021, 286 pp., paperback, ISBN: 9789403631431.

[2] Gewerbepark Gablingen Website, <https://www.gewerbepark-gablingen.de/>, access 25 Oct. 2023. See also the Passive House Database entry: https://passivehouse-database.org/index.php?lang=en#d_7364, access 25 Oct. 2023.

[3] The Passive House Institute website, <https://passivehouse.com/>, access 20 Oct. 2023.

[4] Passive House Association Los Angeles, passivehouse-losangeles.com, access 20 Oct. 2023.

[5] Nobel Prize Foundation, <https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/physics/2023/>, access 20 Oct. 2023.

[6] Website of ORamaVR, <https://oramavr.com/>, access 20 Oct. 2023.

[7] Richard Stone, 'National pride is at stake.' Russia, China, United States race to build hypersonic weapons, in *Science*, 08 Jan. 2020,

<https://www.science.org/content/article/national-pride-stake-russia-china-united-states-race-build-hypersonic-weapons>, access 20 Oct. 2023.

[8] Nobel Prize Foundation, <https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/chemistry/2020/>, access 20 Oct. 2023.

[9] By Jonathan Calvert and George Arbuthnott, What really went on inside the Wuhan lab weeks before Covid erupted, in *The Times* 2:34PM June 11, 2023,

<https://www.theaustralian.com.au/world/the-times/what-really-went-on-inside-the-wuhan-lab-weeks-before-covid-erupted/news-story/96a38b1d31eed7e7b01c6407b481d3f5>, access 20 Oct. 2023.

- [10] Barton Gellman, *Dark Mirror – Edward Snowden and the American Surveillance State*, Penguin Books, London, 2018.
- [11] <https://www.amazon.com/Dark-Mirror-Snowden-American-Surveillance/dp/B011Q15ILK/>, access 20 Oct. 2023
- [12] Barton Gellman website, <https://www.bartongellman.com/dark-mirror/>, access 20 Oct. 2023.
- [13] Kate Kershner, How the PRISM Surveillance System Works, <https://people.howstuffworks.com/prism-surveillance-system.htm>, access 20 Oct. 2023.
- [14] <https://cdn.netzpolitik.org/wp-upload/prism-slide-7.jpg>, access 20 Oct. 2023.
- [15] M. Tinker (2020) in *That Hideous Strength: A Deeper Look at How The West Was Lost*, EP Books, Leyland, p. 24.
- [16] C. S. Lewis, *The Abolition of Man – Reflections on Education with Special Reference to the Teaching of English in the Upper Forms of Schools*, University of Durham: Riddel Memorial Lectures, Geoffrey Bless: The Centenary Press, London 1947.

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